

1 **Title:** LCIB functions as a carbonic anhydrase: Evidence from yeast and Arabidopsis carbonic
2 anhydrase knock-out mutants

3 **Authors:** Remmy W. Kasili, Ashwani K Rai, James V. Moroney*

4 **Author Affiliation:** Department of Biological Sciences, Louisiana State University, Baton Rouge,
5 Louisiana 70803, USA

6 ***Corresponding Author:** James V. Moroney, btmoro@lsu.edu

7 **Statements and Declarations**

8 **Competing Interests:** The authors declare that they have no competing interests

9

10 **Abstract**

11 *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* evolved a CO₂-concentrating mechanism (CCM) because of the
12 limited CO₂ in its natural environment. One critical component of the *C. reinhardtii* CCM is the
13 limiting-CO₂ inducible B (LCIB) protein. LCIB is required for acclimation to air levels of CO₂.
14 *C. reinhardtii* cells with a mutated LCIB protein have an ‘air-dier’ phenotype when grown in low
15 CO₂ conditions, meaning they die in air levels of CO₂ but can grow in high and very low CO₂
16 conditions. The LCIB protein functions together with its close homolog in *C. reinhardtii*,
17 limiting CO₂-inducible C protein (LCIC), in a hexameric LCIB-LCIC complex. LCIB has been
18 proposed to act as a vectoral carbonic anhydrase (CA) that helps to recapture CO₂ that would
19 otherwise leak out of the chloroplast. Although both LCIB and LCIC are structurally similar to
20 βCAs, their CA activity has not been demonstrated to date. We provide evidence that LCIB is an
21 active CA using a *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* CA knockout mutant ($\Delta NCE103$) and an
22 *Arabidopsis thaliana* βCA5 knockout mutant (*βca5*). We show that different truncated versions
23 of the LCIB protein complement $\Delta NCE103$, while the full-length LCIB protein complements
24 *βca5* plants, so that both the yeast and plant mutants can grow in low CO₂ conditions.

25
26 Keywords: CO₂-concentrating mechanism, carbonic anhydrase, *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*,

27 LCIB, LCIC, $\Delta NCE103$

28

29 Introduction

30 The green alga *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* (*Chlamydomonas* hereafter) evolved an
31 efficient photosynthetic process because of the limiting-CO₂ conditions it experiences in its natural
32 aquatic environment. The alga enhances its photosynthetic process by concentrating CO₂ around
33 the enzyme ribulose 1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase (Rubisco) that fixes CO₂ into sugars.
34 Since Rubisco catalyzes both carboxylation and oxygenation reactions, the alga has evolved to
35 increase the CO₂ concentration around Rubisco in order to increase the enzyme's rate of
36 carboxylation while decreasing the rate of the wasteful oxygenation reaction (Moroney and
37 Ynalvez 2007). The mechanism by which green algae concentrate CO₂ around Rubisco to make
38 photosynthesis more efficient is called a CO₂-concentrating mechanism (CCM). The CCM of
39 *Chlamydomonas* is composed of three components: bicarbonate transporters, carbonic anhydrases
40 (CAs) and a sub-cellular micro-compartment called the pyrenoid where the enzyme Rubisco is
41 sequestered. In *Chlamydomonas*, the CCM is activated when the cells are grown in limiting-CO₂
42 conditions: that is, in low CO₂ (LC) conditions (0.03-0.04% [v/v] CO₂ in air) and in very low CO₂
43 (VLC) conditions (<0.02% [v/v] CO₂ in air; Moroney and Somanchi 1999; Spalding 2008). In this
44 report, high CO₂ (HC) refers to 5% (v/v) CO₂ in air, low CO₂ (LC) refers to 0.03-0.05% (v/v) CO₂
45 in air and very low CO₂ (VLC) refers to <0.02% (v/v) CO₂ in air.

46 One critical component of the CCM that functions when *Chlamydomonas* cells are grown
47 in LC conditions is the limiting-CO₂ inducible B (LCIB) protein. A *Chlamydomonas* mutant
48 lacking a functional LCIB protein has an unusual growth phenotype – it grows in HC and VLC
49 conditions but dies in LC conditions. The *lcib* mutant is therefore said to have an ‘air-dier’
50 phenotype (Van et al. 2001; Spalding et al. 2002; Wang and Spalding 2006), indicating that the
51 LCIB protein is indispensable for acclimation to air level CO₂ conditions (i.e., LC conditions) but

52 not necessary for survival in VLC conditions. Experimental evidence shows that the LCIB protein
53 is present in very small amounts in HC conditions but strongly accumulates in LC and VLC
54 conditions when the CCM is induced (Yamano et al. 2010; Wang and Spalding 2014a).

55 The LCIB protein is a soluble protein localized in the chloroplast stroma (Wang and
56 Spalding 2006) that can change from being dispersed throughout the stroma to accumulating in
57 the peri-pyrenoid region depending on light and CO₂ concentration (Yamano et al. 2022; Yamano
58 et al. 2010). LCIB is dispersed throughout the stroma when cells are grown in light and HC
59 conditions, but it forms a ring around the pyrenoid when cells are moved to LC or VLC conditions
60 in the light (Yamano et al. 2010; Wang and Spalding 2014b). When cells are transferred from light
61 and HC conditions to darkness and LC/VLC conditions, LCIB remains dispersed in the chloroplast
62 stroma, confirming that the relocation is light-dependent (Yamano et al. 2010). LCIB localization
63 also depends on the presence of the starch sheaths that surround the pyrenoid. In a starchless
64 mutant called *sta11-1*, LCIB aggregated at the basal region of the chloroplast after 24 h in VLC
65 conditions as opposed to forming a ring around the pyrenoid, while in a mutant with a thin starch
66 sheath (*sta2-1*), LCIB formed a ring-like structure around the pyrenoid after 24 h in VLC
67 conditions (Toyokawa et al. 2020). These observations suggest that LCIB localization is dependent
68 not only on light and CO₂ concentration but also on the presence of the starch sheaths that form
69 around the pyrenoid under LC and VLC conditions (Toyokawa et al. 2020). Recently, Yamano et
70 al. (2022) demonstrated that the relocation of LCIB is also dependent on the presence of the
71 limiting-CO₂ inducible C (LCIC) protein. Overall, neither the regulation of LCIB relocation nor
72 the mechanism that allows the protein to respond to changes in light and CO₂ concentration are
73 completely understood.

74 LCIB forms a complex with its close homolog LCIC, and this complex is reported to be a
75 350 kD hexamer (Yamano et al. 2010; Wang and Spalding 2014b). The LCIB-LCIC complex does
76 not dissociate during relocation when cells are moved from HC to LC conditions (Yamano et al.
77 2010). It was demonstrated that LCIB physically interacts with LCIC and with itself (Yamano et
78 al. 2010). LCIC protein levels are greatly reduced or totally depleted in *lcib* mutants despite normal
79 LCIC mRNA induction, indicating that the observed reduction or depletion of LCIC protein levels
80 probably arises from changes that occur at the posttranslational level (Yamano et al. 2022).

81 In *Chlamydomonas*, LCIB has three closely related homologs: LCIC, LCID and LCIE.
82 These three homologs are also found in diatoms, bacteria, and hornworts (Wang and Spalding
83 2006; Yamano et al. 2010; Li et al. 2020). However, the functions of these LCIB homologs in
84 *Chlamydomonas* or in other organisms have not been determined.

85 LCIB is proposed to play a critical role in the *Chlamydomonas* CCM by preventing the
86 leakage of the CO₂ from the pyrenoid when the CCM is induced (Wang and Spalding 2006;
87 Yamano et al. 2010; Wang and Spalding 2014a and b; Toyokawa et al. 2020). Inorganic carbon
88 (C_i) is brought into the *Chlamydomonas* cell by two bicarbonate transporters called high-light
89 activated 3 (HLA3) and low-CO₂ induced 1 (LCI1) which are located on the plasma membrane.
90 Once inside the cell, the bicarbonate is transported into the chloroplast stroma by LCIA (NAR1.2),
91 a bicarbonate transporter located in the chloroplast envelope. Three bestrophin-like proteins
92 (BST1-3); (Mukherjee et al. 2019) located on the thylakoid membrane are proposed to transport
93 the bicarbonate into the thylakoid lumen, where the acidic pH favors dehydration of the
94 bicarbonate to form CO₂, catalyzed by the luminal α -CA CAH3 (Funke et al. 1997; Karlsson et al.
95 1998). This results in a localized increase in the CO₂ concentration within the pyrenoid. The
96 pyrenoid is traversed with thylakoid tubules (Engel et al. 2015). However, not all CO₂ is fixed –

97 some diffuses out of the pyrenoid (Wang et al. 2015). One physiological role suggested for LCIB
98 is the recapture of CO₂ leaking from the pyrenoid and hydration of that CO₂ to bicarbonate, which
99 is sent back to the stromal C_i pool and ultimately transported back into the thylakoid lumen (Wang
100 and Spalding 2006; Yamano et al. 2010; Wang and Spalding 2014; Toyokawa et al. 2020). LCIB
101 or the LCIB/LCIC complex is reported to interact with BST3 while LCIC is said to interact with
102 BST1 (Mackinder et al. 2017). LCIB is also proposed to associate with the thylakoid tubules that
103 penetrate the pyrenoid (Yamano et al. 2010). These associations might help position the
104 LCIB/LCIC complex around the pyrenoid so it can recapture CO₂ leaking from the organelle. It
105 has also been proposed that LCIB-LCIC forms a physical barrier around the pyrenoid, thereby
106 blocking the leakage of CO₂ (Duanmu et al. 2009; Yamano et al. 2010). The LCIB-LCIC protein
107 complex therefore serves to maintain a high concentration of C_i in the stroma which results in high
108 CO₂ levels in the pyrenoid and a more efficient photosynthetic process.

109 In this report, we present evidence that LCIB is an active carbonic anhydrase. We show
110 that LCIB can complement a *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (yeast hereafter) strain with a lethal CA
111 knockout mutation that prevents growth in LC. We also show that full length LCIB complements
112 *Arabidopsis thaliana* (*Arabidopsis* hereafter) β CA5 knockout plants (*beta5*) to grow in air levels
113 of CO₂. These results also support the idea that LCIB can function as a CA even outside of a
114 complex with LCIC.

115

116 **Materials and Methods**

117 **Chlamydomonas strains and growth conditions**

118 Chlamydomonas growth and culture conditions were like those reported by (Ma et al. 2011) with
119 slight modifications. CLiP WT (CC-5325), an *lcib* CLiP mutant (LMJ.RY0402.173287), an *lcic*

120 CLiP mutant (LMJ.RY0402.235430), an *lcid* CLiP mutant (LMJ.RY0402.045389), an *lcie* CLiP
121 mutant (LMJ.RY0402.182050) and an *lcib/lcid* double mutant were all purchased from the
122 Chlamydomonas Resource Center (<https://www.chlamycollection.org>; Li et al. 2016). Maps
123 showing the insertion locations in each of the LCI genes can be found in Figure S1. All cultures
124 were maintained on Tris-Acetate-Phosphate (TAP) media plates (with 1.5% [w/v] agar) in LC
125 conditions (0.04% [v/v] CO₂ in air) except the *lcib* mutant and the *bd* double mutants that were
126 maintained in HC conditions (5% [v/v] CO₂ in air). For spot tests, a colony of cells was cultured
127 in 5 mL of liquid TAP media and shaken vigorously for 3 days, pelleted, and washed in Minimal
128 (MIN) media (without acetate). The OD₇₃₀ of 1 mL of MIN media with cells was adjusted to 0.15
129 and serially diluted to 10⁻³, then 10µl of each dilution was spotted on MIN plates at three pH levels:
130 7.2, 7.8 and 8.4. The pH differential in the media is significant because the pK_a of the bicarbonate-
131 to-CO₂ interconversion is about 6.4 ($\text{HCO}_3^- + \text{H}^+ \leftrightarrow \text{H}_2\text{CO}_3 \leftrightarrow \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$). The pH of the media
132 determines the availability of C₁ – in acidic media, CO₂ is more available; as the pH increases above
133 6.4, HCO₃⁻ becomes more abundant. The different pH values were used to evaluate the effect of
134 the availability of CO₂ and HCO₃⁻ on the growth of the *lcib* mutant. The plates were incubated in
135 HC, LC and VLC (<0.02% [v/v] CO₂ in air) conditions for 5-8 days.

136 **Yeast strains and growth conditions**

137 A mutant version of the yeast strain DDY2 with its sole CA knocked out (called *ANCE103*) was
138 used in this study. Yeast minimal (YM) media was made by autoclaving 790 mL of water and
139 allowing it cool to 54°C before adding 100 mL of yeast nitrogen base stock (6.88 g/L), 100 mL of
140 20% (w/v) dextrose and 10 mL of an amino acid mix lacking histidine and tryptophan. YM plates
141 were made by adding 1.5% (w/v) agar to the water before autoclaving. The *ANCE103* mutant used
142 in this study was grown at 5% (v/v) CO₂ in air at 30°C. Liquid cultures were grown on a rotary

143 shaker at 30°C in 5% CO₂ and in LC (0.04% CO₂ [v/v] in air). For spot tests, yeast cells were
144 grown on YM plates at 30°C in three different CO₂ conditions: 5%, 1% and LC (0.04% CO₂ [v/v]
145 in air).

146 **Generation of yeast expression constructs**

147 *Chlamydomonas* limiting-CO₂ inducible B (*LCIB*), its homolog limiting-CO₂ inducible C (*LCIC*)
148 and the yeast carbonic anhydrase (*NCE103*) genes were cloned via PCR, amplified from the
149 respective gene cDNA, cloned into the yeast expression vector pDD506 using *Cla*I and *Xho*I
150 restriction sites and verified by sequencing. In order to create truncated versions of *LCIB* and
151 *LCIC*, the genes were cloned using primers with 5' ends that contained a Kozak sequence and, a
152 start codon. This was followed by a gene-specific sequence (Table S1). Δ LCIB and Δ LCIC are
153 missing 50 and 37 amino acids at their N-termini, respectively, compared to the native versions of
154 *LCIB* and *LCIC*. Δ 50LCIB and Δ 37LCIC constructs were used to transform *ANCE103*. The
155 different truncated versions of LCIB (Δ 42LCIB, Δ 45LCIB, Δ 54LCIB, Δ 63LCIB, Δ 68LCIB,
156 Δ 71LCIB and Δ 74LCIB) were created and cloned into pDD506 plasmids as above.

157 ***ANCE103* transformation**

158 The pDD506 plasmids containing full length coding sequences of *LCIB*, *LCIC*, *NCE103*, truncated
159 *LCIB* (Δ 50LCIB) and truncated *LCIC* (Δ 37LCIC) were each transformed into dh5 α *E. coli*
160 competent cells. The plasmids were extracted from the *E. coli* cultures using a GeneJET Plasmid
161 Miniprep Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) according to the manufacturer's
162 instructions. The plasmids were transformed into the *ANCE103* mutant following the protocol
163 described by Gietz and Schiestl (2007) and positive colonies were confirmed by colony PCR using
164 gene-specific primers (Table S1). The pDD506 plasmids containing Δ 42LCIB, Δ 45LCIB,

165 $\Delta 54LCIB$, $\Delta 63LCIB$, $\Delta 68LCIB$, $\Delta 71LCIB$ and $\Delta 74LCIB$ were transformed into *dh5 α E. coli*
166 competent cells and then into *ANCE103* as above.

167 **Yeast spot test and growth assays**

168 Yeast cell cultures were initiated from glycerol stocks and cultured on YM agar plates at 30°C and
169 5% CO₂ for 5 days to select colonies. The colonies were then used to start liquid cultures that were
170 grown at the same conditions as above until the cells reached log phase. For spot tests, the OD₆₀₀
171 of all cultures was taken and adjusted to 0.01 in 1 mL of YM media with cells. That 1 mL was
172 then serially diluted up to 10⁻³ and 10 μ l of each dilution was spotted on YM plates. The plates
173 were incubated at 30°C in 5% CO₂, 1% CO₂ and LC (0.04% [v/v] CO₂ in air) for 96 h. For liquid
174 growth assays, cultures had their OD₆₆₀ adjusted to 0.01 in 50 mL of YM media with cells. Cultures
175 were then incubated at 30°C in 5% CO₂ and LC (0.04% CO₂ [v/v] in air). Growth rates were
176 determined by measuring the cultures' OD₆₆₀ every 24 h using a spectrophotometer (Thermo
177 Fisher Scientific) for a total of 120 h.

178 **Genetic constructs for Arabidopsis transformation**

179 The full-length coding sequence of *LCIB* from *Chlamydomonas* with and without a stop codon
180 was cloned into the GATEWAY entry vector pENTR following the manufacturer's protocol and
181 transformed into *dh5 α E. coli* competent cells. Error-free colonies were confirmed by sequencing
182 before recombination into GATEWAY-compatible destination vectors pMDC32 and pMDC83.
183 The resulting plasmids were transformed into *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* by the freeze-thaw
184 method (Weigel and Glazebrook 2006) and then into plants via the floral dip method (Zhang et al.
185 2006).

186 **Gene expression in *ANCE103***

187 *ΔNCE103-EV* and *ΔNCE103-Δ50LCIB* growing in liquid YM media were pelleted to remove the
188 media and resuspended in 1 mL of TRIzol (Invitrogen, Waltham, MA, USA), then the cells were
189 transferred to 2 mL Eppendorf tubes containing 200 μL of glass beads. The cells were disrupted
190 by glass beating using a vortex set at maximum speed (5 cycles of 1 min vortex, 1 min rest). Then
191 200 μL of chloroform was added and the mixture was vortexed for 30 sec followed by incubation
192 at room temperature for 5 min. The cells were then centrifuged at maximum speed for 5 min at
193 4°C. The supernatant was transferred to a fresh tube to which an equal volume of ice-cold
194 isopropanol was added followed by incubation on ice for 15 min. The tube was centrifuged at
195 maximum speed for 5 min and the resulting pellet was washed with 1 mL of 70% (v/v) ethanol.
196 The pellet was left to dry on the bench for 30 min and later dissolved in 50 μL of RNase-free water.
197 The RNA concentration was determined using a NanoDrop (Thermo Fisher Scientific). For
198 quantitative reverse transcription PCR (qRT-PCR), the RNA concentration was adjusted to 100
199 ng/μL and 1 μL was used in a 20 μL reaction. The qRT-PCR was set using the LUNA Universal
200 One Step RTPCR kit protocol from New England Biolabs (<http://www.neb.com/e3005>) and run
201 using QuantStudio 6. The primers used for LCIB were 5' GTGTCCTGACCTGCGGTG 3'
202 (forward) and 5' CCGAGTTGATGGCAATGTGG 3' (reverse) and the primers used for ACTIN
203 were 5' AGAGTTGCCCCAGAAGAACA 3' (forward) and 5' GGCTTGGATGCAAACGTAGA
204 3' (reverse).

205 **Western blot analysis**

206 Total protein extraction from yeast followed the method used by Zhang et al. (2011). Protein
207 extractions were resolved by SDS-PAGE on a 12% (v/v) polyacrylamide gel. The expression of
208 LCIB was detected after transfer of the proteins onto a PVDF membrane using a Semi-Dry system
209 (Bio-Rad). The membrane was blocked overnight at 4°C in TTBS (TBS with 0.05% [v/v] Tween)

210 containing 0.1% (w/v) bovine serum albumin (BSA). The next day, the membrane was treated
211 with an anti-LCIB monoclonal antibody at a dilution of 1:1000 (a gift from Martin Spalding) for
212 1 h at room temperature and washed 4 times with TTBS. The membrane was then treated with a
213 secondary anti-rabbit antibody at a dilution of 1:2000 (HRP conjugated from Bio-Rad) for 1 h and
214 washed 4 times with TTBS. Fluorescence-based detection of antibody binding was done using
215 Thermo Scientific™ Pierce™ ECL Western blotting substrate on a Chemi-Doc XRS (Bio-Rad,
216 Hercules, CA, USA). The ladder used to determine the size of the LCIB protein was the Precision
217 Plus Dual Color Standards from Bio-Rad.

218 For plant proteins, 40 mg of fresh leaf tissue was placed in a sterile 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tube
219 and ground using a sterile plastic pestle. 132 μL of Protein Extraction Buffer (1x TE, 1.2% [w/v]
220 SDS, 2.7% [w/v] sucrose, 7.5 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ bromophenol blue) was added to the ground leaf tissue.
221 Samples were vortexed and incubated on ice for 15 min. Samples were then centrifuged at 14,000
222 rpm for 5 min using a benchtop centrifuge and the supernatant was transferred into a sterile 0.5
223 mL microcentrifuge tube. Protein concentrations were quantified using the Pierce Coomassie Plus
224 (Bradford) Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific). 2-mercaptoethanol was added to a final
225 concentration of 350 mM and then samples were incubated at 100°C for 2 min. 40 μg of total
226 protein was loaded into pre-cast wells in a 12% (v/v) polyacrylamide gel and proteins were
227 electrophoresed before being transferred to a PVDF membrane using a Semi-Dry system (Bio-
228 Rad). The LCIB monoclonal antibody was used at 1:500 dilution while the secondary antibody
229 and detection of antibody binding was done as above.

230 **Rosette area and dry weight measurements**

231 Plant images for each plant line were taken weekly for 5 weeks, and rosette areas were determined
232 using MatLab (PhenoImage; Zhu et al. 2021). To measure dry weights, the above ground mass of

233 each plant was incubated at 34°C for a week then weighed. Three plants per line were used to
234 determine mean rosette area and mean dry weight.

235 **Confocal Microscopy**

236 eGFP fluorescence was visualized in leaves from *βca5* plants stably transformed with a
237 35S::LCIB:eGFP construct using a Leica SP2 confocal microscope. The white light laser was used
238 with 5% laser power and smart gain was adjusted to 100%. A 20X objective lens was used to
239 visualize the cells from leaf samples. eGFP and chlorophyll were excited using a krypton/argon
240 laser tuned to 488 nm, and eGFP and chlorophyll fluorescence were observed between the
241 wavelengths of 500–520 nm and 660–700 nm, respectively.

242

243 **Results**

244 **Growth analysis of the *Chlamydomonas lcib* mutant and the *bd* double mutant**

245 Growth analysis of the *Chlamydomonas lcib* mutant and *bd* double mutant was carried out at HC,
246 LC and VLC conditions and at different pH levels. In these experiments, the *cia5* mutant was used
247 as negative control. The *cia5* mutant is a knockout of the gene CIA5, a transcription factor that
248 controls the expression of most CCM genes (Fukuzawa et al. 2001; Xiang et al. 2001; Moroney et
249 al. 1989). The *lcib* mutant died in air levels of CO₂ (0.04% [v/v] CO₂ in air, or LC conditions) at
250 the three pH levels tested (7.2, 7.8 and 8.4), hence the ‘air-dier’ phenotype. The ‘air-dier’
251 phenotype had earlier been reported by Wang and Spalding (2006). In HC conditions, the growth
252 of the *lcib* mutant was like that of the WT at all pH levels (Figs. 1A and B). In VLC conditions,
253 *lcib* grew at all pH levels but its growth was reduced compared to WT. When mutants of the LCIB
254 gene family (*lcic*, *lcid* and *lcie*) were analyzed at the same pH levels, they all had the same
255 phenotype as WT in every CO₂ condition (Fig. 1A). LCID was among the genes identified by Fang

256 et al. (2012) to belong to a set of low-CO₂-inducible (LCI) genes. It belongs to the LCIB gene
257 family together with LCIC and LCIE. Wang and Spalding (2006) observed that LCID had similar
258 expression levels to LCIB and LCIC in WT cells under LC and VLC conditions. Since only the
259 *lcib/lcid* double mutant was readily available from the Chlamydomonas Resource Center, we
260 choose to use it in place of an *lcic/lcib* double mutant. The *bd* double mutant mimicked the *lcib*
261 mutant at all pH levels and in all CO₂ conditions: it had an ‘air-dier’ phenotype in LC conditions,
262 showed reduced growth in VLC conditions, and grew like WT in HC conditions (Fig. 1B). The
263 ‘air-dier’ growth phenotype suggests that the LCIB protein is needed for successful acclimation to
264 LC conditions in Chlamydomonas (Wang and Spalding 2006; Wang and Spalding 2014a).

265 **Different fragments of LCIB complement *ΔNCE103* in LC conditions**

266 Heterologous complementation of the yeast strain *ΔNCE103* provides a reliable test for putative
267 CA activity (Rai et al. 2022). The yeast mutant, which is missing its sole CA (encoded by the gene
268 *NCE103*), requires 5% CO₂ to grow (Rai et al. 2022). It dies in 1% CO₂ and LC levels because it
269 requires HCO₃⁻ for various biosynthetic pathways (Aguilera et al. 2005). *ΔNCE103* complemented
270 with its own CA (ScCA hereafter) grows in all CO₂ conditions (5%, 1% and LC; Aguilera et al.
271 2005; Rai et al. 2022). To test whether LCIB has CA activity, we transformed *ΔNCE103* with full
272 length LCIB. Full length LCIB failed to complement *ΔNCE103* in LC conditions (data not shown).
273 Therefore, additional modifications were needed to generate a functional LCIB in yeast. LCIB is
274 a chloroplast-localized protein in Chlamydomonas and since yeast does not possess a chloroplast,
275 the chloroplast targeting sequence of LCIB had to be removed for the protein to complement the
276 yeast mutant. We determined that we needed to remove 50 and 37 amino acids from the N-termini
277 of LCIB and LCIC, respectively, using ChloroP1.1

278 (<https://services.healthtech.dtu.dk/service.php?ChloroP-1.1>) before the ChloroP1.1 application
279 was discontinued.

280 **$\Delta 50$ LCIB complements *ANCE103* in LC conditions, $\Delta 37$ LCIC does not**

281 We transformed *ANCE103* with a truncated LCIB ($\Delta 50$ LCIB) and a truncated LCIC ($\Delta 37$ LCIC),
282 which are missing 50 and 37 amino acids at their N-termini respectively. *ANCE103*- $\Delta 50$ LCIB
283 grew in all CO₂ conditions (5% CO₂, 1% CO₂ and LC; Fig. 2A). However, *ANCE103* transformed
284 with $\Delta 37$ LCIC (*ANCE103*- $\Delta 37$ LCIC) grew in 5% CO₂ but died in 1% and LC conditions, like the
285 empty vector (EV) control strain (*ANCE103*-EV; Fig. 2A). *ANCE103* transformed with both
286 $\Delta 50$ LCIB and $\Delta 37$ LCIC (*ANCE103*-B+C) grew like the positive control strain ScCA on solid YM
287 media (Fig. 2A).

288 Growth curves in liquid media reflected the results seen in solid media. When grown in liquid YM
289 media in LC conditions, *ANCE103*-EV and *ANCE103*- $\Delta 37$ LCIC showed no change in the OD₆₆₀
290 measured over a 120 h period (Fig. 2B). In contrast, *ANCE103*- $\Delta 50$ LCIB and *ANCE103*-B+C had
291 steady growth under LC conditions, with *ANCE103*-B+C showing faster growth compared to
292 *ANCE103*- $\Delta 50$ LCIB (Fig. 2B). However, both *ANCE103*-B+C and *ANCE103*- $\Delta 50$ LCIB grew
293 slower than the positive control strain ScCA in LC conditions. In 5% CO₂, all strains grew;
294 however, *ANCE103*-B+C reached the highest cell density after 5 days in culture (Fig. 2C).

295 We wanted to determine the number of amino acids that can be deleted from the N-terminus of
296 LCIB for the protein to still complement *ANCE103* to grow in LC conditions. ChloroP1.1 predicted
297 the length of the chloroplast transit peptide sequence (CTP) to be 50 amino acids. We therefore
298 removed a minimum of 42 amino acids ($\Delta 42$ LCIB) and a maximum of 74 amino acids ($\Delta 74$ LCIB)
299 and all fragments with removals between 50-68 amino acids tested in this study complemented
300 *ANCE103* in LC conditions and gave a phenotype like the ScCA positive control on YM plates

301 (Fig. 3). All of the fragments remaining after removal of 50-68 amino acids from LCIB that we
302 tested still complemented *ΔNCE103* (Fig. S2). It appears the length of the chloroplast transit
303 peptide sequence lies within or beyond this range because the remaining protein fragments are
304 functional. We could not test different fragments of LCIB due to resource limitations.

305 **LCIB mRNA and protein are made in *ΔNCE103* transformed with *Δ50LCIB***

306 To confirm that LCIB is present in *ΔNCE103* transformed with *Δ50LCIB* (*ΔNCE103-Δ50LCIB*),
307 we analyzed LCIB expression using qRT-PCR and Western blotting. The qRT-PCR results
308 showed that LCIB mRNA is made in *ΔNCE103-Δ50LCIB* (Fig. S3). A Western blot confirmed
309 that LCIB protein is made in *ΔNCE103-ΔLCIB* (Fig. 4). We found a protein band of ~45kD using
310 an anti-LCIB antibody, similar to the mature LCIB size reported by Wang and Spalding (2014b).

311 **Full length LCIB complements Arabidopsis *βca5* mutant in LC conditions**

312 To test whether LCIB is an active CA in plant plastids, we transformed an Arabidopsis strain
313 missing the carbonic anhydrase β CA5 (called *βca5*). β CA5 is a plastid CA and it is the only plastid
314 CA that is present in Arabidopsis roots (Weerasooriya et al. 2022). Arabidopsis plants missing
315 β CA5 cannot grow in LC. Like the yeast CA knockout (CAKO) strain *ΔNCE10*, the *βca5* mutant
316 requires HCO_3^- for fatty acid biosynthesis. Arabidopsis *βca5* plants transformed with full length
317 LCIB driven by the 35S promoter (*βca5-LCIB* hereafter) grew in LC (Fig. 5A). When WT, *βca5*-
318 LCIB and *βca5* plants were subjected to growth analysis in LC, *βca5* plants exhibited poor growth,
319 while *βca5-LCIB* plants showed a growth phenotype similar to WT plants. When growth
320 parameters such as dry weight of above ground matter and rosette areas were determined, we found
321 that there was no significant difference between WT plants and *βca5-LCIB* plants at the end of the
322 5-week growth period. WT plants do appear to have higher rosette areas than *βca5-LCIB* at the
323 end of the 5-week growth period, though these differences are not statistically significant. Both

324 WT and *βca5*-LCIB had significantly higher dry weights and rosette areas than *βca5* plants (Fig.
325 5B-C). Confocal microscopy showed that LCIB is localized in the chloroplasts of Arabidopsis
326 leaves (Fig. 6) and a Western blot showed that LCIB protein is expressed in *βca5*-LCIB plants
327 (Fig. 7). Six lines were generated that showed complementation but only one line was used for the
328 above tests.

329

330 **Discussion**

331 Chlamydomonas cells with a non-functional LCIB protein die in LC conditions (Fig. 1A),
332 demonstrating that LCIB is a critical component of the Chlamydomonas CCM during acclimation
333 to LC conditions (Wang and Spalding 2014a). The observation that *lcib* dies in air levels of CO₂
334 but grows in HC and VLC conditions has led researchers to describe the mutant as having an ‘air
335 dier’ phenotype (Spalding et al. 1983). Unsurprisingly, *lcib* demonstrates defective C_i
336 accumulation in LC conditions (Duanmu et al. 2009).

337 In VLC conditions, the growth of *lcib* is reduced compared to WT cells, as was earlier
338 reported by Wang and Spalding (2014a). Current thinking posits that *lcib* grows in VLC conditions
339 because Chlamydomonas cells resort to an active bicarbonate uptake system rather than the passive
340 CO₂ uptake system that requires LCIB (Wang and Spalding 2014a). The proposed bicarbonate
341 uptake system involves HLA3 on the plasma membrane, LCIA on the chloroplast envelope
342 (Spalding 2008; Wang and Spalding 2014a) and BST1-3 (Mukherjee et al. 2019) located on the
343 thylakoid membrane. These bicarbonate transporters work to enrich the stromal C_i pool with
344 bicarbonate, which is then dehydrated to CO₂ to be fixed by Rubisco in the pyrenoid, enabling
345 cells to grow in a VLC environment. Our results, together with those of others, support the idea
346 that LCIB is not needed for survival in VLC conditions (Wang and Spalding 2014a), though it

347 does potentially help bolster the efficiency of the CCM by preventing CO₂ leakage from the
348 pyrenoid in both VLC and LC conditions (Yamano et al. 2010; Wang and Spalding 2014b).

349 In *Chlamydomonas*, LCIB has four close homologs: LCIB, LCIC, LCID and LCIE. In WT
350 cells, LCIB and LCIC show similar expression patterns: low expression in HC conditions and high
351 expression in LC and VLC conditions (Wang and Spalding 2006; Brueggeman et al. 2012).
352 LCID's expression pattern is like that of LCIB and LCIC, but it is expressed less overall (Miura et
353 al. 2004). LCIE shows very low expression in all CO₂ conditions (Wang and Spalding 2006). Apart
354 from LCIB, the other homologs have no known function in the *Chlamydomonas* CCM. We
355 obtained CLiP mutants with insertions in *LCIB*, *LCIC*, *LCID* and *LCIE* (Fig. S1). A spot test
356 showed that all mutants except *lcib* had phenotypes that looked like that of WT cells in each tested
357 CO₂ condition and pH level (pH 7.2, 7.8 and 8.4; Fig. 1A). Our analysis was limited to spot tests;
358 therefore, we could not fully elucidate the functions of the other LCIB homologs in the
359 *Chlamydomonas* CCM. Further analysis is needed to delineate the roles of LCIC, LCID and LCIE
360 in the *Chlamydomonas* CCM.

361 We also wanted to analyze the growth phenotype of the *bd* double mutant. Our spot test
362 analysis of *bd* revealed that the double mutant had a similar phenotype to that of the *lcib* single
363 mutant: it dies in air levels of CO₂ but grows in HC and VLC conditions. The *lcid* single mutant
364 does not have an impaired growth phenotype, but rather grows like WT cells in all CO₂ conditions
365 tested (Fig. 1b). The *lcib* single mutant phenotype masks the *lcid* single mutant phenotype (i.e.,
366 the *bd* double mutant has a similar phenotype as the *lcib* mutant). However, the function of LCID
367 in the *Chlamydomonas* CCM remains unknown because the *lcid* mutant lacks a growth phenotype.
368 We suggest that more LCID insertional lines should be screened, as our results are limited to a
369 single insertional line.

370 LCIB is proposed to play a role in CO₂ recapture in *Chlamydomonas* by capturing the CO₂
371 unfixed by Rubisco that escapes from the pyrenoid as well as the CO₂ diffusing in the stroma. The
372 captured CO₂ is then hydrated to bicarbonate, which enriches the C₁ pool in the stroma so that
373 ultimately the CO₂ concentration around Rubisco is increased and photosynthesis is more efficient
374 (Wang and Spalding 2014a; Spalding 2008; Moroney et al. 2011; Duanmu et al. 2009). This
375 proposed function of LCIB in CO₂ recapture implies that the protein demonstrates vectoral CA
376 activity. Unlike a typical CA which interconverts CO₂ and HCO₃⁻, a vectoral CA functions in a
377 unidirectional manner. In this case, LCIB is proposed to convert CO₂ to HCO₃⁻ and not vice versa
378 (Duanmu et al. 2009; Yamano et al. 2022). It has also been suggested that LCIB helps with CO₂
379 recapture by forming a physical barrier around the pyrenoid to prevent CO₂ leakage (Yamano et
380 al. 2010). Although the protein structure of LCIB resembles that of βCAs (Jin et al. 2016), its CA
381 activity has not been demonstrated previously in *Chlamydomonas*.

382 We wanted to find out if LCIB demonstrates CA activity, so we probed the protein's ability
383 to restore growth in a yeast CAKO mutant (Δ *NCE103*). Yeast has a single CA (NCE103) that
384 converts CO₂ to bicarbonate, which is then used in the biosynthesis of vital organic compounds
385 and molecules such as nucleotides and fatty acids (Aguilera et al. 2005). Δ *NCE103* requires 5%
386 CO₂ to grow; in limiting-CO₂ conditions like 1% and LC, the mutant dies (Aguilera et al. 2005;
387 Rai et al. 2022). When Δ *NCE103* was transformed with full length LCIB, it still required 5% CO₂
388 to grow and died in limiting-CO₂ conditions (results not shown). However, when Δ *NCE103* was
389 transformed with Δ 50LCIB (a truncated version of LCIB missing 50 amino acids at its N-
390 terminus), it grew in 5% CO₂, 1% CO₂ and LC, implying that the required level of carbonic
391 anhydrase activity in the cell was fulfilled by Δ 50LCIB. Because yeast has no chloroplast, it was
392 necessary to remove the chloroplast-targeting sequence to create a modified LCIB protein that

393 could function in $\Delta NCE103$. The $\Delta 50$ LCIB protein enabled $\Delta NCE103$ to grow like the positive
394 control ScCA, meaning the cell's CA activity was restored.

395 We went on to further investigate the length of the leader sequence required for LCIB to
396 complement $\Delta NCE103$. We truncated LCIB by removing different numbers of amino acids from
397 its N-terminus and established that LCIB fragments missing between 50-68 amino acids from their
398 N-termini still possessed CA activity and complemented $\Delta NCE103$ to grow in LC. However,
399 $\Delta 71$ LCIB, $\Delta 42$ LCIB and $\Delta 45$ LCIB could not enable $\Delta NCE103$ to grow in 1% CO₂ or LC (data
400 not shown). This is probably caused by the extra N-terminal amino acids left on $\Delta 42$ LCIB or
401 $\Delta 45$ LCIB, which might interfere with protein folding and render the fragments non-functional.
402 The $\Delta 71$ LCIB fragment is missing three amino acids (valine, alanine and histidine) which are
403 present in $\Delta 68$ LCIB and likely contribute to its functionality in a manner that has not yet been
404 resolved. Our results indicate that LCIB alone has CA activity. Because yeast is a eukaryote, it
405 appears it is able to provide the biochemical environment needed for LCIB to function as a CA.

406 $\Delta NCE103$ transformed with full length LCIC showed the same growth phenotype as the
407 $\Delta NCE103$ -EV negative control strain (data not shown). $\Delta NCE103$ transformed with $\Delta 37$ LCIC (a
408 truncated version of LCIC missing 37 amino acids at its N-terminus) likewise only grew in 5%
409 CO₂ and failed to grow in limiting-CO₂ conditions. This result implies that either LCIC has no CA
410 activity, it has too little CA activity to complement $\Delta NCE103$ or that the removal of 37 amino
411 acids from the N-terminus did not make the remaining protein fragment functional in $\Delta NCE103$
412 (Fig. 2A). It may be that more or less amino acids need to be removed to render the remaining
413 fragment functional. Jin et al. (2016) reported that $\Delta 52$ LCIB and $\Delta 40$ LCIC did not show CA
414 activity *in vitro* using isotope-exchange membrane-inlet mass spectrometry (MIMS) and the
415 Wilbur-Anderson method. This observation suggests that truncated LCIB and LCIC may require

416 the presence of other proteins or factors to show CA activity. It could also be that the disordered
417 regions of LCIB and LCIC that were removed from their C-terminals by Jin et al. (2016) play a
418 role in the functionality of the two proteins. Or still, it is possible that the fragments of both proteins
419 had such low CA activity that it could not be captured by the instruments employed.

420 We wanted to compare the growth of $\Delta NCE103\text{-}\Delta 50\text{LCIB}$, $\Delta NCE103\text{-}\Delta 37\text{LCIC}$ and
421 $\Delta NCE103\text{-B+C}$ in a liquid growth assay. $\Delta NCE103\text{-}\Delta 37\text{LCIC}$ did not grow in limiting- CO_2
422 conditions. However, $\Delta NCE103\text{-B+C}$ grew better than $\Delta NCE103\text{-}\Delta 50\text{LCIB}$ when analyzed for
423 120 h at 30°C in LC conditions. When the same experiment was conducted at 5% CO_2 , $\Delta NCE103\text{-}$
424 B+C displayed better growth than $\Delta NCE103\text{-}\Delta 50\text{LCIB}$ and the positive control ScCA. This
425 observation suggests that $\Delta 50\text{LCIB}$ functions better when in a complex with $\Delta 37\text{LCIC}$, even
426 though $\Delta 37\text{LCIC}$ alone fails to support $\Delta NCE103$ growth in limiting- CO_2 conditions. LCIB and
427 LCIC are known to form an LCIB-LCIC complex in *Chlamydomonas* (Wang and Spalding 2014b)
428 and LCIB is reported to strongly interact with LCIC (Wang and Spalding 2014b; Yamano et al.
429 2010; Mackinder et al. 2017). Since the $\Delta 50\text{LCIB}\text{-}\Delta 37\text{LCIC}$ complex complements $\Delta NCE103$, it
430 is reasonable to assume the complex demonstrates CA activity. However, Jin et al. (2016) reported
431 that a recombinant LCIB-LCIC complex failed to show CA activity *in vitro*, implying that it might
432 have needed other factors to function under the experimental conditions used in the study.

433 It is possible that the LCIB-LCIC complex requires other proteins to function or that they
434 need to be anchored, given that they are both soluble proteins (Yamano et al. 2010). The starch
435 sheath surrounding the pyrenoid likely provides anchorage for the LCIB-LCIC complex,
436 evidenced by the close proximity of the starch sheath and the immunogold-labeled LCIB-LCIC
437 complex as shown by Yamano et al. (2010). However, no experimental evidence of LCIB-LCIC
438 anchorage in the starch sheath has been demonstrated to date. It has also been suggested that the

439 microtubules that traverse the pyrenoid provide anchorage for the LCIB-LCIC complex (Yamano
440 et al. 2010), although there is no direct evidence. The lack of an anchoring structure in the *in vitro*
441 assay performed by Jin et al. (2016) might account for the observed absence of LCIB-LCIC CA
442 activity. Since yeast is a eukaryote like *Chlamydomonas*, it is possible that it could provide the
443 additional factors needed for a functional $\Delta 50\text{LCIB}-\Delta 37\text{LCIC}$ complex. We tested $\Delta 50\text{LCIB}$ and
444 $\Delta 50\text{LCIB}-\Delta 37\text{LCIC}$ from $\Delta NCE103$ for CA activity using the Wilbur-Anderson method but there
445 was no CA activity detected. The failure of $\Delta 50\text{LCIB}$, $\Delta 50\text{LCIB}-\Delta 37\text{LCIC}$, and $\Delta 37\text{LCIC}$ to
446 display CA activity requires further investigation, as this will enrich our understanding of the roles
447 that LCIB and its homologs play in the CCM. There is also a possibility that CA activity is not
448 detected because very low CA activity might be needed for $\Delta NCE103$ to grow in LC conditions.

449 To further demonstrate that the *Chlamydomonas* LCIB protein has CA activity, we used
450 the protein to complement an *Arabidopsis* *βca5* mutant. *Arabidopsis* and tobacco have two plastid
451 CAs that are in the stroma, βCA1 and βCA5 (Hines et al. 2021; Weerasooriya et al. 2022). In
452 *Arabidopsis*, βCA5 is expressed in both roots and shoots, but it is the only plastid CA present in
453 the roots (Weerasooriya et al. 2022) where it is proposed to supply bicarbonate needed for nucleic
454 acid and fatty acid biosynthesis (DiMario et al. 2017). The *βca5* mutant plants require high CO_2
455 conditions (at least 20,000 ppm or 2% CO_2) to grow, otherwise plants are stunted and sterile when
456 grown in LC conditions (Medina-Puche et al. 2017; Weerasooriya et al. 2022). We transformed
457 *βca5* plants with a $35\text{S}::\text{LCIB}:\text{eGFP}$ construct and observed that the transformed plants grew like
458 WT plants in LC (Fig. 5), implying that LCIB complements *βca5*. We also observed with confocal
459 microscopy that LCIB correctly localized to the chloroplast of the transgenic *Arabidopsis* plants.
460 To further confirm that *βca5*-LCIB plants were as healthy as WT plants, we carried out a growth
461 comparison of *βca5*, *βca5*-LCIB and WT plants. When dry weight and rosette areas were analyzed,

462 we observed that *βca5* plants had the lowest growth parameters of the three plant types, as
463 expected. *βca5*-LCIB and WT plants did not show significant differences in their dry weight and
464 leaf rosette areas during a period of 5 weeks post-germination. Thus, LCIB appears to complement
465 *βca5* plants to grow with the same healthy phenotype as WT plants. The *βca5* single mutant plants
466 have a diminutive phenotype even with the presence of other cytoplasmic and chloroplastic CAs,
467 implying that βCA5 is needed for a WT growth phenotype. This work shows that LCIB's CA
468 activity can substitute for Arabidopsis βCA5 in the plastids of *βca5* mutant plants. Taken together
469 our results demonstrate that LCIB alone has CA activity in yeast and in plants.

470

471 **Conclusion**

472 LCIB is required for acclimation to LC conditions in *Chlamydomonas*. A dysfunctional LCIB
473 protein results in an 'air-dier' phenotype in mutant cells. This implies that LCIB is an important
474 component of the CO₂-concentrating mechanism (CCM) when *Chlamydomonas* cells acclimate to
475 LC conditions. We have demonstrated that LCIB functions as a CA using a yeast CAKO mutant
476 (*ΔNCE103*). Various truncated versions of LCIB allow *ΔNCE103* to grow in LC conditions, likely
477 by restoring CA activity in the mutant cells. We also used Arabidopsis β-carbonic anhydrase 5
478 (*βca5*) knockout plants, which grow poorly and are nonviable in LC conditions, to demonstrate
479 the CA activity of LCIB. We have shown that transformation of these mutant plants with full
480 length LCIB restores their growth in LC, so that the mutants grow like WT plants. This is the first
481 demonstration that *Chlamydomonas* LCIB has CA activity.

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638

639 **Figure legends**

640

641 **Figure 1a** Growth analysis of the LCiB gene family. CLiP WT, CLiP mutants *lcib*, *lcic*, *lcid*,
642 *lcie* and *cia5* cells were diluted to 6.6×10^5 cells per milliliter followed by three 1:10 serial
643 dilutions. 10 μ L of each dilution was spotted for growth comparison in very low CO₂ (VLC), low
644 CO₂ (LC), and high CO₂ (HC) at pH 7.2, 7.8 and 8.4. The cells were grown for 5-8 days. The
645 CCM-deficient *cia5* mutant was used as a control

646

647 **Figure 1b** Growth analysis of *lcib*, *lcid* and *lcib/lcid* (*bd*). CLiP WT, *lcib*, *lcid* and *bd* cells were
648 spotted as in Figure 1a and grown in very low CO₂ (VLC), low CO₂ (LC), and high CO₂ (HC) at
649 pH 7.2, 7.8 and 8.4 for 5-8 days. The CCM-deficient *cia5* mutant was used as a control

650

651 **Figure 2a** Growth analysis of $\Delta NCE103$ transformed with LCiB, LCiC, and LCiB+C. $\Delta NCE103$
652 strains transformed with the native *S. cerevisiae* carbonic anhydrase (*ScCA*), an empty vector
653 (EV), $\Delta 50$ LCiB, $\Delta 37$ LCiC and $\Delta 50$ LCiB+ $\Delta 37$ LCiC (B+C) were grown in liquid YM media in
654 5% CO₂ at 30°C for 3-5 days. The OD₆₀₀ of 1 mL of yeast cells was adjusted to 0.01 followed by
655 three 1:10 serial dilutions. 10 μ L of each dilution was spotted on YM plates and incubated in
656 5%, 1% and low CO₂ (LC) at 30°C for 5 days. $\Delta 50$ LCiB and $\Delta 37$ LCiC are *C. reinhardtii* LCiB
657 and LCiC proteins missing 50 and 37 amino acids at their N-termini, respectively

658

659 **Figure 2 b and c** Liquid growth analysis of $\Delta NCE103$ transformed with LCiB, LCiC, and
660 LCiB+C. $\Delta NCE103$ strains transformed with the native *S. cerevisiae* carbonic anhydrase (*ScCA*),
661 an empty vector (EV), $\Delta 50$ LCiB, $\Delta 37$ LCiC and $\Delta 50$ LCiB+ $\Delta 37$ LCiC (B+C) were grown in
662 liquid YM media in 5% CO₂ at 30°C for 3-5 days. The OD₆₀₀ was adjusted to 0.01 in 50 mL of
663 YM media then the cells were incubated at 30°C for (b) 120 h in LC and for (c) 120 h in 5%
664 CO₂. Points in the graph represent means and error bars represent standard errors (n=3).
665 Statistical significance for the last point at 120 h in 2b and 2c was computed by ANOVA
666 (p<0.05). Statistical differences are represented by different letters

667

668 **Figure 3** $\Delta NCE103$ transformed with different truncated versions of LCiB can grow in ambient
669 CO₂ levels. $\Delta NCE103$ was transformed with $\Delta 42$ LCiB, $\Delta 45$ LCiB, $\Delta 50$ LCiB, $\Delta 54$ LCiB,
670 $\Delta 63$ LCiB, $\Delta 68$ LCiB, $\Delta 71$ LCiB and $\Delta 74$ LCiB, which are truncated versions of LCiB missing 42,
671 45, 50, 54, 63, 68, 71 and 74 amino acids from their N-termini, respectively. Growth of these
672 transformed $\Delta NCE103$ strains was analyzed via spot tests on YM plates. Bars represent the
673 chloroplast targeting sequence of LCiB, which is 448 amino acids long. Truncated versions of
674 LCiB that restored growth of $\Delta NCE103$ in LC conditions are shown in green to indicate positive
675 complementation

676

677 **Figure 4** LCiB protein is detected in $\Delta NCE103$ transformed with $\Delta 50$ LCiB. Lane 1 was loaded
678 with protein from $\Delta NCE103$ transformed with $\Delta 50$ LCiB and lane 2 was loaded with protein from
679 $\Delta NCE103$ transformed with *ScCA*. The membrane was probed with an anti-LCiB antibody. An
680 SDS-PAGE gel loaded with the same protein samples and stained with Coomassie blue is shown
681 below the Western blot as a loading control

682

683 **Figure 5 a and b and c** Full-length LCiB complements Arabidopsis *βca5* mutant plants to grow
684 in ambient CO₂. (a) The plants were imaged 5 weeks after germination. Dry weights (b) and

685 rosette areas (**c**) of Arabidopsis *βca5* mutant plants, *βca5*-LCIB plants and WT Col plants. Dry
686 weight was determined after keeping the above ground matter in an incubator at 34°C for 7 days.
687 Rosette areas were measured every week for a period of 5 weeks. Lines represent the averages
688 from three plants of each type and bars show standard errors

689

690 **Figure 6** Confocal microscopy shows LCIB localization in the chloroplasts of Arabidopsis *βca5*-
691 LCIB plants expressing a 35S::LCIB:eGFP construct

692

693 **Figure 7** LCIB protein is detected in Arabidopsis *βca5* plants transformed with full length LCIB.
694 Lane 1 was loaded with protein from untransformed *βca5*, lane 2 was loaded with protein from
695 *βca5* plants transformed with 35S::LCIB:eGFP and lane 3 was loaded with protein from WT
696 Arabidopsis. The membrane was probed with an anti-LCIB antibody

697

698 **Supplementary Figure 1** CLiP mutants *lcib*, *lcic*, *lcid* and *lcie* contain inserts that disrupt
699 expression of *LCIB*, *LCIC*, *LCID* and *LCIE*, respectively. Grey boxes represent 3' and 5'
700 untranslated regions, blue boxes represent exons, black lines represent introns and red triangles
701 represent insertion cassettes. *lcib* (LMJ.RY0402.173287) and *lcic* (LMJ.RY0402.235430)
702 contain insertion cassettes in the fourth exons of *LCIB* and *LCIC*, respectively. *lcid*
703 (LMJ.RY0402.045389) contains an insertion cassette in the first exon of *LCID*. *lcie*
704 (LMJ.RY0402.182050) contains an insertion cassette in the seventh exon of *LCIE*. Insert
705 locations were originally reported with 95% confidence in Li et al. (2019). The insertion
706 locations were confirmed by sequencing the mutants

707

708 **Supplementary Figure 2** Different truncated versions of LCIB complement the $\Delta NCE103$
709 mutant. $\Delta NCE103$ strains transformed with the native *S. cerevisiae* carbonic anhydrase (*ScCA*),
710 $\Delta 50$ LCIB, $\Delta 54$ LCIB, $\Delta 63$ LCIB, $\Delta 68$ LCIB, and an empty vector (EV) were grown in liquid YM
711 media in 5% CO₂ at 30°C for 3-5 days. The OD₆₀₀ of 1 mL of yeast cells was adjusted to 0.01
712 followed by three 1:10 serial dilutions. 10 μ L of each dilution was spotted on YM plates and
713 incubated in in 5%, 1% and low CO₂ (LC) at 30°C for 5 days. $\Delta 50$ LCIB, $\Delta 54$ LCIB, $\Delta 63$ LCIB,
714 and $\Delta 68$ LCIB are truncated versions of LCIB missing 50, 54, 63, and 68 amino acids from their
715 N-termini, respectively

716

717 **Supplementary Figure 3** LCIB mRNA is made in $\Delta NCE103$ - $\Delta 50$ LCIB. $\Delta NCE103$ -EV and
718 $\Delta NCE103$ - $\Delta 50$ LCIB cells were grown in liquid YM media for 4 days in 5% CO₂ at 30°C. RNA
719 extraction was done using TriZol. Actin was used as a reference gene. The lines shown represent
720 the average of three replicates. Experimental set up is as explained in Materials and Methods

721

722 **Supplementary Table 1** Primers used for cloning fragments of LCIB and LCIC. The Kozak
723 sequence and the start codon were inserted at the 5' end of each primer. The Kozak sequence is
724 bold, the start codon is red and the gene specific sequence is gray. All LCIB fragments had the
725 same reverse primer